

Development of a Monte Carlo Solver for Neutron Noise Based on RMC and Research on Its Full-Frequency Convergence and Efficiency

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ABSTRACT

Convergence poses a critical challenge in Monte Carlo simulations of neutron noise, being influenced by multiple factors including weight representation, noise transport methods, roulette schemes, and variance reduction techniques. Despite ongoing developments, existing Monte Carlo solvers for neutron noise have not yet achieved full-frequency convergence. Inspired by prior research on orthodox linear noise equation, we first analytically proved the full-frequency convergence of the flight-based method in any systems without weight cancellation. We then implemented both flight-based and collision-based neutron noise transport methods in the general-purpose Monte Carlo code RMC, together with real/imaginary-part-based and norm-based roulette methods. Furthermore, we introduced optimizations that significantly improved the computational efficiency of the flight-based method. Numerical tests were performed on a 2D assembly benchmark with implicit capture and forced fission enabled. The convergence behavior and computational efficiency of three different method combinations were evaluated. It was observed that the real/imaginary-part-based roulette significantly impairs convergence. Results confirm that the flight-based method with norm-based roulette achieves full-frequency convergence. Moreover, its computational efficiency is comparable to that of the collision-based method at low and intermediate frequencies, and becomes clearly superior at higher frequencies.

Keywords: neutron noise, Monte Carlo method, convergence, RMC

1. INTRODUCTION

In power reactors, minor perturbations in macroscopic cross-sections induce slight fluctuations in neutron flux, termed reactor neutron noise. These perturbations can arise from random variations in coolant density, vibrations of fuel rods, control rods, and other internal components [1]. By monitoring neutron flux variations with in-core and ex-core detectors, non-intrusive surveillance of potential anomalies is enabled, contributing to operational safety. This technique also facilitates the measurement of coolant properties such as void velocity [2] and void fraction.

To circumvent time-intensive neutron dynamics calculations, neutron noise equation is commonly solved in the frequency domain. Previous deterministic codes based on diffusion or transport theory [3–5] fell short in high fidelity (with phase-space discretization or diffusion approximation) and modeling flexibility for complex geometries. In 2013, Yamamoto [6] introduced the first Monte Carlo (MC) approach for solving the neutron noise equation, employing the flight-based method (FBM) for noise transport simulation. Rouchon [7] later proposed the collision-based method (CBM). However, both methods face particle number explosion at very low or high perturbation frequencies, leading to non-convergence in fixed-source simulations [6, 7].

To address convergence, Yamamoto [6] introduced a regional weight cancellation technique, while Rouchon [7] achieved convergence at low or high frequencies by disabling implicit capture and tuning the parameter η . Belanger [8] later integrated the collision-based method with weight cancellation in the MGMC code [9]. Although these methods improved convergence, a systematic theoretical

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understanding of the properties of convergence remained lacking. Fauvel [10] conducted a comprehensive theoretical analysis of convergence in MC method for an infinite homogeneous media, comparing flight-based method and collision-based method. Additionally, they found that the norm-based roulette method (NRM) outperforms real/imaginary-part-based roulette method (RIRM, default in all current MC solvers) in convergence behavior. Their recent work about the theoretical framework of convergence of Monte Carlo algorithms is in [11].

In this work, we firstly analytically prove the full-frequency convergence of the flight-based method for any systems, showing its corresponding eigenvalue of noise equation is always less than 1. Then we implement both the flight- and collision-based methods in the general-purpose Monte Carlo code RMC [12] and incorporate norm-based and real/imaginary-part-based roulettes. Given the low transport and tally efficiency of the flight-based method, we further optimize it. Based on a realistic benchmark, we compare the convergence and computational efficiency of various method configurations. It shows that the flight-based method combined with norm-based roulette ensures full-frequency convergence while maintaining computational efficiency comparable to the collision-based method.

The paper is structured as follows: Sec. 2 introduces the two neutron noise transport methods and, inspired by [10], provides a generalized proof of the flight-based method's full-frequency convergence. Sec. 3 describes the implementation of both transport and roulette methods in RMC, along with efficiency optimizations for the flight-based method. A 2D assembly benchmark is used to evaluate different method configurations across frequencies, comparing their convergence and efficiency. Conclusions are presented in Sec. 4.

2. MONTE CARLO METHOD FOR NEUTRON NOISE

The derivation of noise equation in the frequency-domain originates from the spatio-temporal neutron kinetics equation with delayed neutrons, as shown in [1]. Small periodic perturbations $\delta\Sigma$ in macroscopic cross section and $\delta\varphi$ in flux are introduced on their steady values:

$$\Sigma = \Sigma_0 + \delta\Sigma. \quad (1)$$

$$\varphi = \varphi_0 + \delta\varphi. \quad (2)$$

Substitute Eq. (1) and Eq. (2) into the kinetics equation. Then, reduce the expression using the steady-state equation and neglect the second-order perturbation terms. Finally, neutron noise equation for $\delta\varphi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{\Omega}, E, \omega)$ in frequency domain is derived via Fourier transform:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{i\omega}{v} + \mathbf{\Omega} \cdot \nabla + \Sigma_t\right) \delta\varphi = & \iint \Sigma_s f_s \delta\varphi d\mathbf{\Omega}' dE' + \frac{\chi_p}{4\pi k_{\text{eff}}} \iint v_p \Sigma_f \delta\varphi d\mathbf{\Omega}' dE' \\ & + \sum_j \frac{\lambda_j}{\lambda_j + i\omega} \frac{\chi_d^j}{4\pi k_{\text{eff}}} \iint v_d^j \Sigma_f \delta\varphi d\mathbf{\Omega}' dE' + Q_\omega, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Where all symbols have their usual signification. In practical simulations, the system eigenvalue often deviates from unity. To enforce a steady state, the equation is normalized by k_{eff} . Here, ω denotes the angular frequency from the Fourier transform, and Q_ω represents the noise source arising from the Fourier-transformed perturbed cross-section:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_\omega = & -\delta\Sigma_t \varphi_0 + \iint \delta\Sigma_s f_s \varphi_0 d\mathbf{\Omega}' dE' + \frac{\chi_p}{4\pi k_{\text{eff}}} \iint v_p \delta\Sigma_f \varphi_0 d\mathbf{\Omega}' dE' \\ & + \sum_j \frac{\lambda_j}{\lambda_j + i\omega} \frac{\chi_d^j}{4\pi k_{\text{eff}}} \iint v_d^j \delta\Sigma_f \varphi_0 d\mathbf{\Omega}' dE'. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

As shown, the noise source comprises three components: the copy term, the scattering term, and the fission term. The fission term is further divided into prompt and delayed parts. Notably, the delayed fission term introduces imaginary weights, while the copy term yields weights of opposite sign. During the sampling of noise source particles in Monte Carlo method, these three source types are sampled

separately within the perturbed regions, generating particles with varying weights, which contributes to increased variance in subsequent fixed source calculations.

Formally, the neutron noise equation constitutes a fixed-source problem. Firstly, perform a criticality (eigenvalue) calculation to obtain the fundamental flux distribution φ_0 . Then sample the neutron noise source according to φ_0 , which serves as the source for the subsequent noise transport simulation. To accumulate sufficient statistics for uncertainty quantification, this entire procedure must be repeated over multiple independent batches.

2.1. Neutron Noise Transport Methods

In Monte Carlo games for neutron noise, particles have complex weights. The core distinction between neutron noise transport and standard neutron transport lies in the treatments of the term $i\omega\delta\varphi/v$ and the complex delayed-fission factor $\lambda_j/(\lambda_j + i\omega)$ by which is multiplied when sampling fission particles. Two principal methods have been developed to handle the term $i\omega\delta\varphi/v$: the flight-based method and the collision-based method. A brief introduction to each approach is provided below. The weights of sampled delayed fission particles undergo multiplication by the complex delayed-fission factor of the sampled precursor group.

Proposed by Yamamoto, the flight-based method treats $i\omega/v$ as an additional cross-section [6]. As a result, the phase of particle's complex weight undergoes continuous shift during flight: if a particle has an initial weight w_i and samples a flight distance s_i using only the total cross-section Σ_t , its weight w_{i+1} upon reaching the next site is given by:

$$w_{i+1} = w_i \exp\left(-\frac{i\omega}{v_i} s_i\right) = w_i \left(\cos\left(\frac{\omega}{v_i} s_i\right) - i \sin\left(\frac{\omega}{v_i} s_i\right) \right). \quad (5)$$

The exponent being purely imaginary implies that the modulus of the particle weight remains unchanged, while its phase continuously evolves.

The collision-based method, introduced by Rouchon, adds the term $(\eta - i)\omega\delta\varphi/v$ to both sides of Eq. (3), where η is a positive real number with the same sign as ω . This allows defining a new total cross-section, $\tilde{\Sigma}_t = \Sigma_t + \eta\omega/v$, which incorporates a special copy reaction corresponding to the term $(\eta - i)\omega\delta\varphi/v$ on the right-hand side. When a copy reaction is sampled, a new particle is generated with the same position, energy, and direction as the incident particle, but with its weight scaled by a factor of $(\eta - i)/\eta$. Since particle weights are updated only after collisions, the mesh tally requires no modification. However, the generation of additional particles may adversely affect computational convergence.

2.2. Convergence of Monte Carlo Method

Convergence poses a critical challenge in Monte Carlo simulations of neutron noise. In fixed-source calculations, the simultaneous presence of both positive and negative weights in the real and imaginary parts of particles—which cannot cancel during transport, unless weight cancellation techniques are used—may lead to continuously increasing particle population, ultimately preventing normal termination.

The convergence of the Monte Carlo method can be evaluated through two distinct sets of eigenvalues: the eigenvalue k of its associated eigenequation, which characterizes overall convergence, and the eigenvalue c of the transport operator within a generation, which describes convergence inside a single generation [11]. In typical reactor physics problems, the condition $|c| < 1$ always holds. This condition also remains valid in neutron noise calculations using the flight-based method, since its transport operator within a generation shares the same $|c|$ as that of standard neutron transport in the same system. Thus eigenvalue c is not considered in the following.

Fauvel [10] derived exact expression of k for linear noise equation in infinite homogeneous media, establishing the relationship between k and k_∞ . The results show that the flight-based method maintains $|k| < 1$, ensuring stability, while the collision-based method suffers from $|k| > 1$ and

diverges at high frequencies. Although increasing η extends the convergence range, it cannot prevent divergence at sufficiently high frequencies for collision-based method.

Building on this work, we further analytically prove the full-frequency convergence of the flight-based method in any systems without weight cancellation. Following derivations employ the same notations as in [10], readers can find detailed definitions of all the operators and kernels in [10]. Standard neutron transport equation as a Fredholm integral equation of the second kind with eigenvalue k_{eff} for the collision density $\psi = \Sigma_t \varphi$ is expressed as:

$$\psi = \mathcal{T} \left(\mathcal{C}_s + \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} (\mathcal{C}_{f,p} + \mathcal{C}_{f,d}) \right) \psi. \quad (6)$$

ψ is defined on the phase-space point $P = (\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, E)$. \mathcal{T} is integral operator with flight kernel T . \mathcal{C}_s , $\mathcal{C}_{f,p}$ and $\mathcal{C}_{f,d}$ are integral operators with collision kernels \mathcal{C}_s , $\mathcal{C}_{f,p}$ and $\mathcal{C}_{f,d}$ represented for scatter, prompt fission and delayed fission contributions respectively.

To account for complex-weighted Monte Carlo games, an additional phase-space coordinate θ is introduced. Therefore, a complex weight w can be described by its modulus $|w|$ and phase $\theta = w/|w|$. The original phase-space point P is transformed to the extended phase-space point $\tilde{P} = (P, \theta)$.

The similar form for neutron noise equation with eigenvalue k and modified operators (with tilde) in the extended phase-space for $\tilde{\delta\psi} = \Sigma_t \tilde{\delta\varphi}$ is:

$$\tilde{\delta\psi} = \tilde{\mathcal{T}}_{fb} \left(\tilde{\mathcal{C}}_s + \frac{1}{k} (\tilde{\mathcal{C}}_{f,p} + \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_{f,d}) \right) \tilde{\delta\psi}. \quad (7)$$

Where $\tilde{\mathcal{T}}_{fb}$ is the flight operator for flight-based method. Eq. (7) can also be written as the form of kernel integral:

$$\tilde{\delta\psi}(\tilde{P}) = \int \left(\tilde{K}_s(\tilde{P}', \tilde{P}) + \frac{1}{k} \tilde{K}_{f,p}(\tilde{P}', \tilde{P}) + \frac{1}{k} \tilde{K}_{f,d}(\tilde{P}', \tilde{P}) \right) \tilde{\delta\psi}(\tilde{P}') d\tilde{P}', \quad (8)$$

Where

$$\tilde{K}_\alpha(\tilde{P}', \tilde{P}) = Z_{\mu_\alpha}(\theta', \theta) K_\alpha(P', P), \quad Z_{\mu_\alpha}(\theta', \theta) = |\mu_\alpha| \delta \left(\theta' \frac{\mu_\alpha}{|\mu_\alpha|} - \theta \right). \quad (9)$$

Subscript α represents the three collision reactions. Kernel $Z_{\mu_\alpha}(\theta', \theta)$ is introduced for the phase shift from θ' to θ due to multiplication by a complex value μ_α . Since the modulus of complex weight is invariant through flight kernel for flight-based method, we can show that $|\mu_s|$ and $|\mu_{f,p}|$ equal to 1, while $|\mu_{f,d}| = \lambda/|\lambda + i\omega|$ (assuming a single precursor group for conciseness). Now we define $\delta\psi(P)$ as:

$$\delta\psi(P) = \int_0^{2\pi} \tilde{\delta\psi}(P, \theta) d\theta. \quad (10)$$

Let us consider the integral of $\tilde{K}_\alpha(\tilde{P}', \tilde{P}) \tilde{\delta\psi}(\tilde{P}')$ over θ' and θ :

$$\begin{aligned} \iint K_\alpha(\tilde{P}', \tilde{P}) \tilde{\delta\psi}(\tilde{P}') d\theta' d\theta &= \iint Z_{\mu_\alpha}(\theta', \theta) K_\alpha(P', P) \tilde{\delta\psi}(\tilde{P}') d\theta' d\theta \\ &= |\mu_\alpha| K_\alpha(P', P) \int \tilde{\delta\psi}(P', \theta) d\theta = |\mu_\alpha| K_\alpha(P', P) \delta\psi(P'). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

All the terms in Eq. (7) are integrated over θ , then we can get:

$$\delta\psi = \mathcal{T} \left(\mathcal{C}_s + \frac{1}{k} \left(\mathcal{C}_{f,p} + \frac{\lambda}{|\lambda + i\omega|} \mathcal{C}_{f,d} \right) \right) \delta\psi. \quad (12)$$

Eq. (12) is similar to Eq. (6) except for the factor $\lambda/|\lambda + i\omega|$ of $\mathcal{C}_{f,d}$. If the spectrums of prompt fission and delayed fission are identical, which is rigorously satisfied in the case of multiple group energy, Eq. (6) and Eq. (12) can be rewritten as:

$$\psi = \mathcal{T} \left(\mathcal{C}_s + \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} \mathcal{C}_f \right) \psi. \quad (13)$$

$$\delta\psi = \mathcal{T} \left(\mathcal{C}_s + \frac{1}{k} \left((1 - \beta) + \frac{\lambda\beta}{|\lambda + i\omega|} \right) \mathcal{C}_f \right) \delta\psi. \quad (14)$$

Where \mathcal{C}_f is the fission operator that does not distinguish between prompt and delayed fission. Since boundary conditions in eigenvalue calculations, such as vacuum, reflective, and periodic boundaries, are time-independent and their mathematical forms are invariant under Fourier transformation, the boundary conditions in Eq. (13) and Eq. (14) are identical. Consequently, we have the same eigenfunctions and eigen-values for Eq. (13) and Eq. (14). Thus,

$$k = \left((1 - \beta) + \frac{\lambda\beta}{|\lambda + i\omega|} \right) k_{\text{eff}} < k_{\text{eff}} = 1. \quad (15)$$

Moreover, since $\lambda_j/|\lambda_j + i\omega| < 1$, which means less yield of delayed fission in noise transport system than in standard neutron transport system, it is obvious that $k < k_{\text{eff}}$. Finally, we can conclude that the flight-based method always ensures convergence across all frequencies in any systems.

Additionally, norm-based roulette method is proposed in [10]. Compared to the real-imaginary part-based roulette method, norm-based method exhibits superior convergence behavior and its necessity for achieving full-frequency convergence will be shown in the subsequent section. However, existing Monte Carlo solvers for neutron noise still rely exclusively on the real-imaginary part-based method.

3. NEUTRON NOISE SIMULATION BASED ON RMC

We have implemented both the flight-based and collision-based neutron noise transport methods in RMC [12]. For particle population control, the conventional real/imaginary part-based roulette method has been incorporated alongside a newly developed norm-based roulette method. To improve load balancing in multi-process calculations, we have adopted the inner generation mode, inspired by the open-source code MGMC [9], which significantly accelerates fixed-source simulations.

For validation, a two-group, 2D simplified 17×17 UOX fuel assembly benchmark, previously used in comparative studies of various neutron noise solvers [13], has been selected. A cross-section perturbation is introduced on fuel pin at (7,7) to serve as the neutron noise source. The relative perturbations in the total, scattering, and fission cross-sections are 0.041, 0.034, and 0.021, respectively.

In this test, we omit weight cancellation technique, since it will suppress the non-physical dominant eigenpair and then influence the original performance of convergence in extended phase-space [10], which is not our intent, although it is beneficial for speeding up convergence in practical simulations.

In the RMC simulations, the cutoff weight was set to 0.25 and the survival weight to 0.5. Each batch simulated 1×10^6 particles at the beginning of a critical calculation, with a total of 100 batches computed. The calculation was performed in parallel using 560 MPI processes. Neutron flux tallies were collected over a 138×138 mesh upon the whole assembly for both the real and imaginary components. The results obtained from RMC show good agreement with those from MGMC within statistical uncertainties, thereby validating the accuracy of the RMC simulations.

3.1. Efficiency Optimization of Flight-Based Method

The flight-based method incurs high computational cost from continuous weight variation during neutron flight. This necessitates frequent weight updates during transport and track-length mesh tallying—a burden especially pronounced in finely subdivided meshes, where crossing each cell demands an update. Consequently, such tallying can consume substantial simulation time, making the

initial flight-based implementation significantly slower than the collision-based method. This aligns with findings in [7], where the flight-based method was also less efficient at intermediate frequencies.

To improve efficiency, we introduced two key enhancements. First, since weight variation across a single mesh cell is typically small under fine discretization, we replace costly trigonometric evaluations in Eq. (5) with their Taylor series approximations when the argument satisfies $x = \omega \cdot s/v < 10^{-3}$, as follows:

$$\sin x \approx x, \quad \cos x \approx 1 - \frac{1}{2}x^2. \quad (16)$$

Benchmark results confirm that the introduced approximation preserves tally values exactly identical to those of the original implementation while reducing total computation time to 83% of the original.

In Monte Carlo ray-tracking, when a sampled mean free path exceeds the distance to the nearest boundary, particles are moved to the boundary for resampling—often requiring multiple flight segments before a collision occurs. Standard implementations perform track-length tallies after each flight segment. Thereby, in flight-based neutron noise simulations, weight updates are necessary after every flight segment. To mitigate this cost, we restructured the ray-tracking workflow: initial particle position and direction are recorded before sampling mean free path, flight segment distances are accumulated upon the total flight distance, and mesh tallies according to the total flight distance are performed only after final sampling, followed by a weight update. This reduces weight update frequency substantially.

With both optimizations implemented, the total computation time is reduced to 65% of the original.

3.2. Test of Full-Frequency Convergence

We evaluated the performance of the two transport methods combined with the two roulette schemes across different perturbation frequencies. Six frequencies were selected: 0.01, 0.1, 1, 50, 100, and 10,000 Hz, covering the full range from low to high frequencies. Three configurations of transport and roulette methods were tested. The weight windows were kept identical between the norm-based and real/imaginary-part-based roulette methods. In the collision-based method, η was set to 1, and both forced fission and implicit capture were applied in all cases. The convergence results are summarized in the Table I.

Table I. Convergence results.

Frequency/Hz	0.01	0.1	1	50	100	10000
FBM + NRM	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
FBM + RIRM	×	✓	✓	×	×	×
CBM + NRM	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	×

The results confirm that the flight-based method, combined with norm-based roulette, achieves convergence across the entire frequency spectrum. In contrast, the real/imaginary-part-based roulette severely impairs convergence. These results thus provide empirical confirmation, on a more realistic benchmark, of the findings reported in [10,11]. Although real/imaginary-part-based roulette preserves the expectation of the complex weight after roulette, it does not preserve that of its modulus, which explains the observed degradation in convergence. In contrast, the norm-based roulette maintains the expected modulus and thus does not compromise the intrinsic convergence [11]. To enable a direct comparison with the flight-based method, norm-based roulette was also applied to the collision-based method. As shown in the results, divergence occurs at high frequencies, which is consistent with the theoretical analysis in [10,11] for an infinite homogeneous media.

Table II. RMS of standard deviations.

Real part			
Frequency/Hz	FBM + NRM	FBM + RIRM	CBM + NRM
0.01	6.98%	—	8.02%
0.1	3.13%	3.37%	2.73%
1	2.78%	3.12%	3.08%
50	3.89%	—	11.83%

Imaginary part			
Frequency/Hz	FBM + NRM	FBM + RIRM	CBM + NRM
0.01	6.37%	—	6.83%
0.1	10.22%	11.26%	8.05%
1	7.96%	13.33%	13.23%
50	2.72%	—	6.60%

Table III. Computation times.

Frequency/Hz	Runtime/min		
	FBM + NRM	FBM + RIRM	CBM + NRM
0.01	144.8757	—	141.7646
0.1	34.3743	35.2445	33.5715
1	30.1009	31.1287	30.237
50	30.1163	—	132.0832

We further compared the computational efficiency of the three configurations in the frequency range of 0.01–50 Hz. The root-mean square (RMS) values of standard deviations of the full mesh tally data are presented in the Table II, and the corresponding computation times are shown in Table III. It can be observed that for low to intermediate frequencies, both neutron noise transport methods exhibit similar accuracy and computational cost. At 0.01 Hz, however, the eigenvalue approaches unity, leading to a notably longer computation time. At 50 Hz, the collision-based method shows degraded convergence: compared to the flight-based method, it not only requires significantly more computation time but also yields noticeably larger variance. According to Eq. (15), the eigenvalue of the flight-based method converges to $k_{\text{eff}}(1 - \beta)$ as frequency increases, which explains the relatively stable computation time after 0.1 Hz.

In summary, the flight-based method with norm-based roulette indeed achieves full-frequency convergence in our tests. After the proposed optimizations, its computational efficiency is at least comparable to that of the collision-based method in the low-to-intermediate frequency range, while offering a clear advantage at higher frequencies. Moreover, it remains applicable in regimes where the collision-based method fails to converge. Our analysis also highlights the impact of the roulette scheme on convergence. Both numerical evidence and theoretical analysis confirm that the flight-based method combined with norm-based roulette is a superior choice for Monte Carlo neutron noise simulations.

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, we implemented both the flight-based and collision-based neutron noise transport methods in RMC, along with two roulette methods: the norm-based and real/imaginary-part-based methods. To address the high computational cost associated with the continuous weight variation during particle flight in the flight-based method, we optimized the ray-tracking algorithm and mesh tallying procedure, achieving a significant improvement in computational efficiency.

Inspired by previous research, we further investigated the relationship between the eigenvalue of noise equation using the flight-based method and k_{eff} , proving that it ensures full-frequency convergence

even in any systems. A realistic 2D benchmark problem was used to test the convergence behavior and computational efficiency of different method configurations across the full frequency spectrum. Numerical results confirm that the flight-based method achieves full-frequency convergence without requiring any ad hoc adjustments. We also show the necessity of the norm-based roulette for full-frequency convergence.

Finally, we compared the computational efficiency of the two neutron noise transport methods. Results show that at low to intermediate frequencies, the optimized flight-based method performs comparably to the collision-based method. However, in regimes where the collision-based method exhibits degraded convergence, the flight-based method demonstrates a clear computational advantage, underscoring its practical superiority for real-world applications.

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